

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

СИНТЕЗ И ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ СВОЙСТВ СОПОЛИМЕРОВ ВИНИЛОВОГО ЭФИРА АСЕТИЛСАЛИЦИЛОВОЙ КИСЛОТЫ С ОЛИГОЭТИЛЕНОВЫМИ МАКРОМОНОМЕРАМИ

Расулзаде Н.Ш.,

к.х.н., доцент,

Азербайджанский Медицинский Университет

Азербайджан, г. Баку

Мирзаева Дж.Н.,

Старший лаборант,

Азербайджанский Медицинский Университет

Азербайджан, г. Баку

Гасымова Г.Р.

Азербайджанский Медицинский Университет

Азербайджан, г. Баку

OBTAINING COPOLYMERS OF VINYL ETHER OF ACETYLSALICYLIC ACID WITH OLIGOETHYLENE MACROMONOMERS AND STUDYING THEIR PROPERTIES

Rasulov N.

Ph.D., Associate Professor,

Azerbaijan Medical University,

Department of Pharmaceutical Toxicology and Chemistry

Baku, Azerbaijan

Mirzeyeva C.

Senior laboratory assistant,

Azerbaijan Medical University,

Department of Pharmaceutical Toxicology and Chemistry

Baku, Azerbaijan

Qasimova H.

Azerbaijan Medical University,

Baku, Azerbaijan

АННОТАЦИЯ

Статья посвящена изучению антибактериальных свойств винилового эфира ацетилсалициловой кислоты (M_1) и реакций его радикальной полимеризации с макромономерами полиэтилена (M_1) и некоторых закономерностей. Показано, что в реакции сополимеризации виниловый эфир ацетилсалициловой кислоты проявляет высокую активность. Константы сополимеризации мономеров определены методом Майо-Люис ($r_1=1,80$ и $r_2=0,01$). Величина относительной активности и их производных, которые близки к нулю, показывают вероятность образования статистических сополимеров. Наблюдается изменение свойств в зависимости от состава сополимеров.

ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the study of the antibacterial properties of acetylsalicylic acid vinyl ether (M_1) and its radical polymerization reactions with polyethylene macromonomers (M_1) and some regularities. It has been shown that vinyl ester of acetylsalicylic acid has high activity in copolymerization reactions. Relative activities of comonomers were determined by the Mayo-Lewis method ($r_1=1.80$ and $r_2=0.01$). Values of relative activities and their product ($r_1 \times r_2 = 0.018$) close to zero indicate a high probability of obtaining static copolymers. It is also observed that the properties of copolymers change depending on its composition.

Ключевые слова: виниловый эфир ацетилсалициловой кислоты, олиго этиленовые макромономеры, сополимер, константа сополимеризации.

Keywords: vinyl acetylsalicylic acid, oligoethylene macromonomer, copolymers, copolymerization constants.

INTRODUCTION

Bacteriocidal and fungicidal additives are usually added to polymeric materials to give them antibacterial properties. It should be noted that the content of type additives in polymer mixtures is measured in percent. Antimicrobial additives are subject to many requirements, the most important of which are that they are

harmless, easy to process, mix with polymers and other additives, do not have a negative effect on the physical and mechanical properties of polymers, and are highly effective [1]. The purpose of including antimicrobial additives in the composition of polymer-based composition materials is to prevent the emergence and development of various types of microbes on the surface and

inside of polymer products. Currently, for this purpose, many antibacterial additives for polyolefins, polystyrene and srirol copolymers have been developed and are widely used. One of the widespread technologies for obtaining antimicrobial polymer materials is the introduction of antibacterial additives into the base polymers during the preparation of polymer products or the coating of the polymer product with an antibacterial layer. Another widespread technology is the introduction of elementary members with a biologically active group into the macrochain at the stage of polymer synthesis [2].

The short-term washing away of the additives from the surface of the antibacterial composition materials made using small molecular additives has a negative effect on other properties, reducing their service life. In order to extend the service life, the use of additional antibacterial polymers in the preparation of antibacterial compositions is considered a promising direction. The use of polymers containing biologically active groups as an antibacterial additive is of great interest. The results of previous studies on the preparation of monomers containing biologically active salicylic group and antibacterial polymers based on them are widely reported in published scientific works [3, 4].

The aim of the presented article refers to the study of the antimicrobial properties of the vinyl ester of salicylic acid (Vasp) and the preparation of its copolymers with polyethylene macromonomers (PEMM).

EXPERIMENTAL PART

Antimicrobial properties of vinyl ester of acetylsalicylic acid, which is the monomer of the synthesized copolymer, was studied by serial dilution method. For this, the substance was studied by a comparative method with 1% phenol and nitrofungin prepared in ethyl alcohol. This was done by diluting a 1% solution

of the substance in ethyl alcohol in sterile distilled water (1:100, 1:200, 1:400, 1:800). The antimicrobial effect of the substance was studied in comparison with ethanol, phenol and nitrofungin. As a test culture, Gram-positive microorganisms, such as staphylococci (*St. aureus*), Gram-negative intestinal bacilli (*E. coli*), pigment-producing blue-green pus bacilli (*Ps. aeruginosa*), and *C. albicans* from the genus Candida was taken from fungi. EPA (meat-peptone agar) was used to cultivate bacteria, and Saburo nutrient medium was used to cultivate fungi.

Inoculations were carried out every 10, 20, 40, 60 minutes, 24 hours at 37°C temperature for bacteria and 48 hours at 28°C temperature for fungi.

To obtain the copolymers of Vasp and PEMM, the reaction mixture containing 9.0 g of PEMM, 1.0 g of Vasp, benzoyl peroxide and 30 ml of decane was poured into a 100 ml glass ampoule. The ampoule is cooled, deaerated with a stream of nitrogen, the mouth is sealed with a weld and placed in a thermostat and heated at a temperature of 70°C for 8 hours. The resulting solid polymer solution was precipitated in ethanol, washed with ether and dried in a vacuum desiccator at 40°C until weight was obtained. Yield 8.2 gr. (82%) happens. The obtained copolymer in the form of a white powder is well soluble in dioxane, chlorinated hydrocarbons, dimethyl sulfoxide and methyl ethyl ketone. It is partially soluble in Na₂CO₃ solution when heated.

PEMM is obtained from the thermal destruction of low-density polyethylene (ASPE) under special conditions. The average molecular mass was about 400, the degree of polydispersity was equal to 1.08 [5].

The IQ spectrum of the synthesized copolymers was recorded in the range of 600-4000 cm⁻¹ on the "Alfa" Bruker spectrometer.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1

Antimicrobial effect of vinyl ester of salicylic acid.

Test cultures	Exposure time (min)	Vynil salicilate				Control comp. Ethanol				Control comp. Phenol			
		-	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
St.aureus	10	-	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
	20	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
	40	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
	60	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Ps.aeruginoza	10	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	+
	20	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+
	40	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	-	+	+
	60	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	+
E.coli	10	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
	20	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
	40	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	-	-	+	+
	60	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	-	-	+	+
Candida albicans	10	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
	20	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
	40	-	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
	60	-	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

Conventional signs: "+" indicates full termination, "-" indicates no termination.

As can be seen from Table 2, the vinyl ester of salicylic acid had a more active antimicrobial effect on Escherichia coli, blue-green pus bacillus and Candida fungus. Thus, Candida fungus was destroyed by 1:400

dilution in 20 minutes, intestinal and blue-green pus bacilli even in 10 minutes, while staphylococci were negatively affected by 1:700 dilution in 20 minutes, but the other dilutions did not affect even one hour.

In the IR spectrum of co-polymers, corresponding absorption bands were obtained at 1640-1660 cm^{-1} (C-

C), 1745 cm^{-1} (C=O) and 1155 cm^{-1} (C-O-C). These results prove that the copolymers have the following structure and composition:

Table 2

Indicators for calculating the relative activities of monomers in the copolymerization reactions of Vasp(M_1) and PEMM (M_2). (Solvent dioxane, $T=70^\circ\text{C}$ reaction time $^{-1}$ hour)

The composition of the primary monomer mixture, mol%	Yield %	Composition of copolymers, mol%		r_1	r_2	r_1r_2	Microstructure of copolymers		
		m_1	m_2				L_1	L_2	R
$M_1:M_2$									
10:90	12,0	52,38	47,62				1,2	1,1	87,3
25:75	8,3	60,63	30,37				1,59	1,03	76,3
50:50	7,0	84,85	15,15	1,8	0,01	0,018	2,8	1,01	52,5
75:25	6,5	86,47	13,53				6,4	1	27,0
90:10	5,8	94,71	5,29				17,2	1	10,9

Lm_1 and Lm_2 - ratio of monomer blocks; R - Harvard block coefficient

Copolymerization constants were calculated using the Mayo-Lewis equation ($r_1=1,80$ v $r_2=0,01$). [6].

Figure 1. Graph of the dependence of the composition of copolymers on the monomer composition taken for the reaction in the copolymerization of vinyl ether of acetylsalicylic acid with PEMM.

As can be seen from Table 1 and Figure 1, the relative activity of the Wasp monomer (M_1) during the copolymerization of the mentioned monomers is higher. The reason for this is that methacrylic monomers have high activity, and on the other hand, alpha-olefins with high mol. mass are passive in radical polymerization. Alfrey-Price parameters for PEMM monomer were calculated ($Q=3,2$ and $e=0,2$). The specific activity value indicates that PEMM is a passive monomer. The specific activity value indicates that PEMM is a passive monomer. On the other hand, the value of the polarity factor (e) in PEMM is close to zero. In this case, since the polarities of both the vinyl ether and the comonomer are close to each other, the

comonomers are less prone to co-polymerization reactions. As a result, the change in the ratio of comonomers in the reaction mixture (increase in the amount of PEMM) causes both the reaction rate and the molecular mass of the obtained copolymers to change.

As can be seen from the figure, the content of PEMM in the copolymers below 50 mol % proves once again that it does not undergo radical homopolymerization reaction. PEMM only enters the copolymerization reaction. An increase in the relative amount of Pemmm in the initial monomer mixture is also observed. From this, it can be concluded that PEMM actively participates in the chain transfer reaction through the monomer, increasing its amount in the monomer mixture

leads to a decrease in the molecular weight of the copolymer (figure 2).

Figure 2. Characteristic viscosity of copolymers obtained in copolymerization reactions of vinyl ester of acetylsalicylic acid with PEMM and dependence of reaction yield on the concentration of the initial monomer mixture.

As can be seen from the figure, the rate of copolymerization reaction increases with the increases.

References

1. Донцова Э.П., Жарненкова О.А., Снежко А.Г., Узденский В.Б. Полимерные материалы с антимикробными свойствами. Пластик, 2014, Т. 131, №1-2, С.30-35.
2. Munoz-Banilla A., Fernandez-Garcia M. Polymer materials with antimicrobial activity/ Progress Polym. Sci. 2012 V37/ p/ 281-339.
3. Расулзаде Н.Ш., Сафарова Г.М. Синтез и исследование потенциальных биологически активных олигоалкиловых эфиров ацетилсалициловой кислоты. XXX VIII Международная научно-практическая конференция «Актуальные проблемы в современной науке и пути их решения» №5(38). 2017 1 часеь. с. 76-78.
4. Rasulzadeh N.Sh., Ibadov E.F. International Journal of Research Studies in Science. Engineering and Technology Volume 4, Issue 3, 2017, PP 1-31.
5. Азизов А.Г., Асадов З.Г., Ахмедова Г.А. Макромомеры. Баку, Елм-2009, 386 с.
6. Торопцова А.М., Белгородская К.В., Бондаренко В.М. Лабораторный практикум по химии и технологии высокомолекулярных соединений-Л., Химия, 1972, 386с.
7. Лисина С.И. Синтез и фармакологическая активность новых производных салициловой кислоты и аспирина лфл потенциальных лекарственных препаратов. Успехи современного Естествознания. - 2006, №11, стр. 125-127.
8. Медицинская микробиология: Учеб. для вузов. О.К. Поздеев; ГЭОТАР МЕД, 2001.768С.
9. Rasulzadeh N.Sh., Azizov A.H., Ibadov E.A., Rasulov N.Sh. The research of antibacterial properties of methyl methacrylate and methacryloyl salicylate copolymers. Azerbaijan chemical journal, №3, 2017. Pp-17-20